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Exploring the Issues in 'On the Job Training' (OJT) Assessment Rubric for Construction Technology Diploma in Malaysian Vocational College

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Abstract

On the job training (OJT) is a pre-requisite requirement for Construction Technology Diploma students to graduate in the Malaysian Vocational College system. The implementation of OJT comprises of assessment processes in assessing students' hands-on performance which uses rubric as an assessment tool. However, based on the literature and documents analysis, it has been identified that the current OJT (organization) assessment rubric is still inadequate in assessing students' competency. The current OJT (organization) assessment rubric is not detailed to the job scope of construction site supervisor. It has been observed that the OJT assessment only uses a single rubric to assessed all diploma programs in the Vocational College. In addition, the current OJT (Organization) assessment rubric is focusing more on the soft skills elements which primarily supposed to gauge more on the hands-on competency of the students. Another issue that has been identified in OJT assessment rubric is that this rubric does not provide descriptors for each of the assessment items according to the scale. As a result, the OJT supervisor from the organization/company does not have clear guidance in assessing students' competency. Therefore, this research suggests that the OJT (Organization) assessment rubric for Construction Technology Diploma should improve on the technical skills elements in order to gauge the competency of construction technology graduates. Furthermore, new descriptors for each technical and soft skills elements need to be identified in order to develop a comprehensive OJT assessment rubric for the Construction Technology Diploma.

Keywords

on the job training; construction technology; Malaysian vocational college; assessment rubric

1 Introduction

The Malaysian construction sector has been thriving since the early days of its independence due to the significance of the sector (Khan, Liew & Ghazali, 2014). In the construction industry, skilled workers who possess specific skill sets, education, training and experience, and also abstract thinking are crucial for effective projects delivery (Zannah, Latiffi, Raji,

Waziri, Mohammed, 2017). Therefore, in fulfilling this need, Malaysian Vocational College has taken the initiative by offering the Diploma in Construction Technology with the aim to produce competent site supervisor for the industries (Bahagian Pendidikan Teknik dan Vokasional, 2017). In graduating from the Construction Technology Diploma program, students need to undertake 'On the Job Training' (OJT) which is an industrial training and during this period, the students will be assessed on their hands-on competency (MOE, 2014). The assessment tool adopted in this OJT is an assessment rubric, and these students will be assessed by the organization/industry supervisor using this rubric (Bahagian Pendidikan Teknik dan Vokasional, 2017). Therefore, this paper will focus on the discussion of issues arise in OJT (Organization) assessment rubric for the Construction Technology Diploma in the Malaysian Vocational College.

2 Vocational College, Construction Technology OJT

A study was done by Awere, Edu-Buandoh, Dadzie, & Aboagye (2016) has identified that graduates are lacked in-depth technical competence in construction technology discipline, lack of maturity and organizational working skills, and they are not able to use the necessary techniques and skills related to technological construction tools for engineering practice. As revealed by Choudhry & Zafar (2017), lack of training affects the new worker's performance in a construction project. In addition, the separation between theory and practice in construction technology course is recognized as a potential problem (Awere, Edu-Buandoh, Dadzie, & Aboagye, 2016). Furthermore, some employers do not handle training programs properly. As for example, supervisors giving tasks that are not related to their course scope and not relevant with the career (Jamaluddin, Ayob, Osman, Omar, Kofli, & Johar, 2013; Verecio, 2014)

3 Vocational College, Construction Technology OJT Assessment

During OJT, the employers and supervisors in the organization play an important role in the assessment process. Employers should give proper guidance on company rules, regulations and procedures since the students who perform industrial training are not yet graduated (Machart, 2017). However, there exist problem regarding organization supervision during the industrial training, which, there is a lacking in eligible staff to supervise the trainees (Bukaliya, 2012). It is believed that most of the assessors are lacking the knowledge in workplace-based assessment procedure (Chinyemba, Bvekerwa, Chirimuta, Sithole, & Gwangwava, 2012). It has been emphasized that supervisory control is a factor that needs to be improved in the practice assessment process of practicum (Verecio, 2014). In addition, the incompetence of assessors and inconsistent assessment process are potential threats to the quality assurance management system (Chinyemba, Bvekerwa, Chirimuta, Sithole, & Gwangwava, 2012).

Workplace-based assessment is often marginalized when the matter is important as it directly affects learning and training (Vaughn & Cameron, 2009). In truth, assessment on skills, knowledge, and ability of workers are the critical components in training packages (Smith & Keating, 2003). In White Card training report for the Australian construction industry, there are a few issues in assessment which have been highlighted (Australian Skills Quality Authority, 2013):

1. Not adequately assess the communication skill and understanding required by the training packages
2. Low quality in the delivery of training and assessment

3. Low reliability in the assessment, in particular, the assessment of the level required in the competence of communication skills.
4. Assessment training and strategies are inconsistent with practices and no strategy to assess communication skills

Assessment of Construction Technology Diploma students during OJT may not provide accurate result as some students spent most of their time at the office compared to the site due to safety reason. As a result, they cannot be assessed for tasks related to the job scope on site. For assessment result reporting purposes, some tools may be used such as checklists, anecdotal records, and rubrics (North Carolina Department of Public Instruction, 1999). OJT assessment also involves the usage of the rubric (MOE, 2014).

4 OJT (Organization) Assessment Rubric

OJT (Organization) assessment rubric is the instrument used in measuring students' hands-on performance during OJT in the organization. However, there are a few issues in the current OJT (Organization) assessment rubric which are :

1. Current assessment rubric was not specific to the job scope of site supervisor. This is because Vocational College used the same rubric for all diploma courses (Technical and Vocational Education Division Academic Management, 2017).
2. Current assessment rubric only consists the soft skills elements. It is believed that the OJT assessment rubric should comprise technical skills elements. This is because, technical skills are equally important as soft skills as perceived by the industry and students (Patacsil, & Tablatin, 2017). Furthermore, according to Bringula et al., (2016), technical skills are similarly important as soft skills for the successful integration of entry-level employees.
3. Current assessment rubric does not provide detail criteria for each scale in every item. Whereas, students' active use and internalization of the assessment criteria is the primary goal of formative rubric use (Fraile, Panadero, & Pardo, 2017). As a result, organization supervisors who are assessing the students during OJT do not have clear guidance in assessing students' competency. According to De Luca & Bolden (2014), the assessor will assess performance inconsistently that will limit the rubric in helping to achieve performance standard if the rubric does not express the criteria clearly.

There are a few importance in studying the development of rubric which is used in the assessment process which are :

1. The rubric is an instrument which is commonly used to assess students' performance based on a task given. The use of rubrics can increase learning and performance under assessment for learning and formative assessment conditions (Panadero & Jonsson, 2013).
2. The usage of a rubric equipped with criteria may guide students in completing a task. This is because a rubric is usually defined as a document with a list of assessment criteria, a scoring strategy and quality definitions normally stated on a scale (Reddy & Andrade, 2010; & Stiggins, 2001).
3. The criteria stated in the rubric can be referred as a guideline for students in improving their grade or marks. This is because, success criteria is one of the emphasized elements when rubrics are used for formative assessment purposes (Fraile, Panadero, & Pardo, 2017).

4. The development of rubric grading criteria for OJT rubric will be able to increase reliability score by having consistent grading criteria based on standard (De Luca & Bolden, 2014).

5 Conclusion

From the literature analysis, it has been identified that assessment rubric is very important in assessing students' competency during OJT. Evidence suggests that the assessment rubric should comprise the technical skills elements as well as soft skills elements because most employers find these two constructs are important in order to be a competent worker. There are needs in highlighting the importance of rubric that equipped with criteria, which may function as a guideline for students in getting better grades. It is believed that the rubric can increase the reliability score by having consistent grading criteria based on the standard. Therefore, further research is suggested to conduct a study on the development of OJT (Organization) assessment rubric with careful considerations from the aspect of constructs, elements, criteria's and scale.

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